

Fabrication, characterization and Physical Properties of Functionally Graded Ti/HAP bioimplants.

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Abstract

In this work, functionally graded materials Ti/HAP were fabricated at $n=0.8, 1$ and 1.2 and characterized by XRD and SEM to evaluate the formed layers in FGMs. Some physical properties were measured for fabricated FGMs include particle size analysis, apparent density, green density, green porosity and shrinkage. The results showed that there are many compounds may be formed between Ti and HAP after sintering at 1000°C for 2 hrs. The XRD analysis indicated the presence of TICP, CaO, Ti_4P_3 and TiO_2 . The SEM images confirm the formation of the later compounds. Because of important of advanced materials such as FGMs as alternative industrial material, it's necessary to measure the properties of these materials. Apparent density was measured for fabricated FGMs and the results indicated that the converting from 1st to 5th layer led to decreasing of apparent density, while the increasing of n value led to increasing apparent density due to increasing of Ti percentage in the layer. Green density and porosity are important factors for materials. The results showed the green density increased with increasing in (n) value, green porosity was decreased with increasing of (n) value because of decreasing in HAP percentage in layer.

Keywords: Functionally graded materials, physical properties of FGM, powder metallurgy.

Introduction

In recent years, functionally graded materials take a wide range in many applications as a new class of advanced materials due to their significant characteristics like bio implant application. Many theoretical works on designing and investigating the performance of FGMs were reported since 1970's but unfortunately, the impact of the outcomes was still limited until present time due to a lack of suitable fabrication method for the FGMs. Many researchers highlighted fabrication and characterization of metal/metal and metal/ceramic FGMs in addition to study their physical, chemical and mechanical properties [1-8].

The functionally graded materials were fabricated at three (n) values which calculated according to Wakashima et al. as follow: [1]

$$V_1(z) = \left(\frac{z_2 - z}{z_2 - z_1} \right)^n \dots\dots(1)$$

where, $V_1(z)$ is the local volume fraction of phase 1 and the volume fraction of phase 2 being:

$$V_2(z) = 1 - V_1(z) \dots(2)$$

(z_1) and (z_2) are border regions of pure phase 1 and phase 2, respectively, z : distance from pure Ti (phase 1) to pure HAP (phase 2) and exponent (n) is a variable parameter, and the magnitude of which determines the curvature of $V_1(z)$.

The aim of present work is: fabrication of Ti/HAP FGMs by powder metallurgy method after limit the n at 0.8, 1 and 1.2 according to mathematical calculations with five layers for FGM. XRD and SEM analysis were used to characterize the fabricated FGMs in addition to study some physical properties of these materials.

2. Experimental

2.1 Fabrication

FGM-samples were prepared using a powder metallurgical process by the layers pressing method. Metallic and ceramic powders were mixed in several proportions. After mixing process, the mixtures were stacked layer by layer with a concentration difference in components content like in Table (1), using pressing method. The powder of layers is measured by sensitive balance type (BEL), which estimated by the following formula:

$$w_L = \rho_L \times V_L \times V_1 \dots (3)$$

Where w_L and ρ_L are weight and density of powder layer, V_L is layer volume and V_1 is volume fraction.

Pure Ti with purity 98.5% and average particle size 165 μm obtained from Fluka chemi AGCH-9470 Buckes was used in fabrication. Hydroxyapatite with purity 99.8% and average particle size 42 μm obtained from India used as ceramic material in fabricated FGMs.

Wet mixing was used by Ball Mills type PM200 with rotational speed of 300 rpm for 1 hr. Cold uniaxial pressing in double action dies has been practiced with 50 mm height, 12 mm interior diameter and 32 mm outer diameter.

Sintering process was achieved in quartz tube which placed in furnace type (Thermco-model mini brute 201) at 400°C for 5 hr and at 1000°C for 2 hr.

2.2 Characterization

X-ray diffraction is performed using on X-ray generator with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation at 40 kW and 20 mA. The target used in the X-ray tube was Cu, therefore $\lambda_{\text{Cu}}=1.54060\text{\AA}$ was used in obtaining the XRD patterns.. Also SEM was achieved by SE detectors at 20000X.

2.3 Physical tests

Particle size was analyzed by Zeta Potential and Submicron Particle Size Analyzers using glycerin as a medium for suspension. Green porosity is determined from the knowledge of the theoretical density of blended powders (mixture) which is calculated by the weight percent of elemental powder multiplied by its theoretical density as follow:

$$\rho_g = \frac{m_g}{V_g} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where: ρ_g = Green density (g/ cm³), m_g = Green mass of the compact (g), V_g = Volume of the compact (cm³).

$$\rho_{tB} = \sum_{i=1}^n Wt_i * \rho_i + Wt_2 * \rho_2 + Wt_3 * \rho_3 + \dots\dots\dots + Wt_n * \rho_n \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

where ρ_{tB} = Theoretical density of blended powder (g/cm³), n = No. of elemental powders, Wt_i = Weight percent (%) and $\rho_{1,2,3,\dots,n}$ = Density of elemental powder (g/ cm³).

So the green porosity is calculated from the following equation:

$$P_g = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_g}{\rho_{tB}} \right) \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

where P_g = Green porosity (%), ρ_g = Green density (g/ cm³) and ρ_{tB} = Theoretical density of blended mixture (g/cm³). Dimensional change could be calculated by accurately measuring the green compact, and then comparing it with the size of the sample after sintering. The diameter of the cylinder before sintering was 12 mm, which decreased after the sintering process. Dimensional change for the sintered compact specimen is calculated from the following equation:

$$\text{Dimensional change (\%)} = \frac{L_s - L_D}{L_D} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

where L_D = Die cavity dimension (mm) and L_s = Sintered specimen dimension (mm).

3. Results and Discussion

XRD of pure Ti and HAP are shown in Figs. (1) and (2). These figures are good agreement with JCPDS-international center for diffraction data with No. of card 44-1294 and 34-0010 for Ti and HAP respectively and they have system of hexagonal.

Figure (3) shows the XRD pattern of layers in FGMs at three values of (n) equal to 0.8, 1 and 1.2 indicating the phases which formed between the two materials Ti and HAP. These figures indicate that HAP partially decomposes into CaO and Ca₄O(PO₄)₂ (TTCP), while some Ti converts to Ti₂O. Also, the constituents react to form Ti₄P₃. As well as, Ti₄P₃ at the Ti/HAP interfaces also forms [9].

Pure HAP has three stages of weight loss; the first stage from 25°C to 200°C is due to the evaporation of absorbed water in the fine powder, the second stage from 800°C to 850°C is due to the release of OH⁻ groups from the HAP crystals, and the third stage above 1000°C is related to the further decomposition of HAP and hence the large loss of the OH⁻ groups [10]. This observation of weight loss during the heating process was in agreement with the decomposition sequence described by

Okazaki et al. [11], who reported that the decomposition reactions of HAP could be divided into two steps, according to the following formulae:

Figs. (4) and (5) show the particle size analysis for the fifth layers of fabricated FGMs Ti-HAP. The mean of particle size for elemental and blended powders are given in Table (2). The best layer is the 3rd with composition of 50%Ti-50%HAP.

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) is used to visualize the microstructure of functionally graded materials by scanning them with high energy beams of electrons in a raster scan pattern. Figures (6) to (8) show the fifth layers in fabricated FGMs. The sintering was achieved at 1000°C for 2 hrs. The sintered composites exhibit a reasonably homogenous distribution of both constituents. As a result of the mixing process the HAP has formed larger agglomerates than those observed in the loose powder, which resulted in the two phase distribution. HAP zones with varied dimensions can be observed and dispersed in a matrix of Ti grains. Darker zones disseminated in the Ti matrix can also be observed, which correspond mainly to the porosity that has not been eliminated during the sintering step. The soft agglomerated ultra-fine HAP particles break up easily during compaction due to high uniform pressure.

Apparent densities are strongly affected by the particle size and its distribution. As a particle shape becomes less spherical, the apparent density decreases due to the gain in the friction surface area and less uniformity powder particle during compaction. Apparent densities of blended powders for mixtures of layers for n equal (0.8, 1, and 1.2) are shown in Fig. (9). The comparison in apparent density among the 2nd, 3rd and 4th indicates that increasing the n value led to increment in apparent density value. Apparent density of 2nd layer mixture is the highest in comparison with the other mixtures due to the high content of the higher solid density (i.e. Ti). The measured apparent density of blended powders and elemental powders has been affected by the following parameters: *a*: Loading rate and internal friction between particles in the same or different composition, *b*: Friction between particles and walls of baffle box and the small funnel. Decreasing surface area to volume ratios and decreasing surface roughness tends to reduce frictional forces between setting particles. This tendency thus increases the apparent density by allowing the particles to move with more effectively to fill the free spaces between the previously settled particles. An effective way to increase the apparent density of the elemental or blended powders is to fill the spaces between particles with smaller particles. Fig. (10) shows that the green density of FGMs increases with increasing of n value from 0.8 to 1.2. While Fig. (11) shows that the green porosity decreases with increasing n value.

This increase in density is likely due to the shrinkage of original pores during sintering. With increasing sintering temperature or sintering time, the shrinkage of the original pores increases. Linear shrinkage is one of the important parameter for evaluating the quality of component gradation in an FGM structure. Shrinkage could be calculated by accurately measuring the green compact, and then comparing it with the size of the sample after sintering. Fig. (12) illustrates the effect of the Ti percentage versus the shrinkage of the diameter of Ti/HAP cylinder which fabricated by powder metallurgy method. This figure indicates that the shrinkage increases with increasing of Ti% and n value.

4. Conclusion

Functionally graded Ti/HAP specimens have been fabricated at three values of n (0.8, 1 and 1.2) by powder metallurgy. Characterization of fabricated FGMs was carried out by XRD and SEM indicating the phases which formed between Ti and HAP after sintering at 1000°C for 2hrs. These phases were mainly TICP, CaO, Ti₄P₃ and TiO₂. Particle size analysis shows irregular behavior for grading from Ti to HAP. The apparent density was decreased for grading from 1st to 5th layer, while it

is increased with increasing n value for fabricated FGMs. The results of green density indicate that increasing in n value led to increasing of density, while green porosity decreases with increasing n value due to decreasing in HAP contents.

5. References

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Table (1): Chemical composition of FGM layers at n values.

No. of layer	Thickness (mm)	n=0.8	n=1	n=1.2
		Composition (%)	Composition (%)	Composition (%)
1 st layer	3	100Ti	100Ti	100Ti
2 nd layer	2.5	67.1Ti-32.9HAP	75Ti-25HAP	81.1Ti-18.9HAP
3 rd layer	2	42.6Ti-57.4HAP	50Ti-50HAP	56.5Ti-43.5HAP
4 th layer	1.5	20.6Ti-79.4HAP	25Ti-75HAP	29.2Ti-70.8HAP
5 th layer	1	100HAP	100HAP	100HAP

Table (2): Average particle size of layers in FGMs at n=1.

No. of Layer	Composition (wt%)	Average particle size (nm)
1 st	Ti	45.1
2 nd	75Ti-25HAP	100.3
3 rd	50Ti-50HAP	118.3
4 th	25Ti-75HAP	131.1
5 th	HAP	198.7

Fig. (1) : XRD pattern of Ti powder.

Fig. (2) : XRD pattern of Hydroxyapatite powder.

n=0.8

n=1

n=1.2

Fig. (3): XRD pattern of layers in FGM at different n.

Fig. (4): Particles size analysis of 100%Ti and 100%HAP.

50Ti-50HAP

25Ti-75HAP

75Ti-25HAP

Fig. (5): Particles size analysis of third powder mixture.

Fig. (6): SEM image for FGMs at n=0.8.

Fig. (7): SEM image for FGMs at n=1.

Fig. (8): SEM image for FGMs at n=1.2.

Fig. (9): Apparent density layers in FGM at different n .

Fig. (10): Green density of FGMs at three values of n ; 0.8, 1 and 1.2.

Fig. (12): Shrinkage of FGM at three values of (n).